

Participant Information Sheet

Human-AI Collaboration for Decision-Making in Agile Sprint Planning

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What is this study about?

We are MSc Software Engineering students at Blekinge Institute of Technology (BTH) conducting a research study on how Agile practitioners respond to AI-generated recommendations during sprint planning. The study examines cognitive bias patterns and trust calibration in Human-AI collaboration.

What will you be asked to do?

You will participate in a semi-structured interview lasting approximately 45–60 minutes. The interview will cover your current sprint planning practice, two short vignette scenarios about AI tool recommendations, and questions about trust in AI tools.

Who is conducting this research?

- **Researchers:** Ungarala Sai Krishna Yashwanth (saun24@student.bth.se) and Mihir Singh Thakur (mith24@student.bth.se)
- **Supervisor:** Henry Edison, PhD, Department of Software Engineering, BTH (henry.edison@bth.se)

Confidentiality and anonymisation

- Your identity and organisation will be fully anonymised in all research outputs. You will be referred to only by a participant code (e.g. P1, P2).
- No sprint records, backlog items, or organisational data will be collected.
- The interview will be recorded with your consent for transcription purposes only. Recordings will be deleted after transcription.
- Full transcripts will not be publicly released. They are available only to the thesis supervisor and examiner upon request.
- An anonymised research data package (interview guide, codebook) will be published publicly on Zenodo after final thesis submission.

Your rights

- Participation is entirely voluntary.
- You may withdraw from the study at any time without consequence and without needing to give a reason.
- You may ask for your data to be removed from the study at any point before final thesis submission.

Data storage

All data will be stored securely and processed in accordance with GDPR requirements. Data will be retained for the duration of the thesis project and will not be used for any purpose other than this research study.

Consent

By agreeing to participate and allowing the interview to be recorded, you confirm that:

- You have read and understood this information sheet.
- You understand what participation involves.
- You understand your right to withdraw at any time.
- You agree to the interview being recorded for transcription purposes.

If you have any questions about the study, please contact the researchers at the email addresses listed above.